

Mapuche

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: South American Religions, Religious Group

The Mapuche have traditionally inhabited south-central Chile. The Mapuche were incorporated into the Chilean government through a reservation system established in the 1880's (Faron, 1960). Despite this reservation system and contact with missionaries, the Mapuche religion remained un-Christianized (Faron, 1964:199). The religious beliefs involve a variety of supernatural beings, including a supreme god, regional deities, deified ancestral spirits, and the spirits of the recently deceased, which are the Mapuche's closest connection to the realm of the supernatural. Religious practitioners are either shamans (machis), who are generally benevolent, lead rituals, and practice medicine, or witches (kalkus), who are generally evil and are involved with malevolent spirits and practices. The most important religious ceremonies among the Mapuche are Ñillatun and Awn. Ñillatun is an agricultural rite for general protection and prosperity, and Awn are funeral rites, which are important for getting souls of the recently deceased to the afterlife. Because religious beliefs are integrated with Mapuche society, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. This entry focuses on the Mapuche living in the vicinity of Temuco, Chile, around the time of 1950.

Date Range: 1925 CE - 1951 CE

Region: Vicinity of Temuco

Region tags: South America, Chile

Vicinity of Temuco, Chile, ca. 1950

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sg04-012>
- Source 1 Description: Faron, L. C. (1964). *Hawks Of The Sun: Mapuche Morality And Its Ritual Attributes*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sg04-001>

– Source 2 Description: Titiev, M. (1951). *Araucanian Culture In Transition. Occasional Contributions From The Museum Of Anthropology Of The University Of Michigan*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sg04-011>

– Source 3 Description: Faron, L. C. (1961). *Mapuche Social Structure: Institutional Reintegration In A Patrilineal Society Of Central Chile. Illinois Studies In Anthropology*. Urbana: The University of Illinois Press.

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sg04-010>

– Source 1 Description: Hilger. (1957). *Araucanian Child Life And Its Cultural Background. Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections*. Washington: Smithsonian Institution.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "If we look to missionary influence, the farthest outpost of directed culture change, we find that the dissemination of Christian belief and action has been in rather sterile ground. All Mapuche ethnologists would agree to this, as would most missionaries working in Mapucheland, including those who are not averse to accepting formal conversion as an indication of eventual spiritual conversion. There has been, in effect, no transition from traditional religious institutions to the Christian systems of belief and ritual action"

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "The failure of the Christian ideal to take hold among the Mapuche is testimony to the successful integration of Mapuche society and its system of values, for religion provides the framework in which the general inculcation of traditional values, attitudes, and procedures is accomplished. Four hundred years of missionary work, economic imperialism, and even ultimate military defeat have failed to crack the hard shell of Mapuche religious morality. The Araucanian language, in which these values are expressed (and which for this reason is banned in the reservation schools), is still the language of the home... There is a general rejection of Chilean values and procedures, patent in an undercurrent of constant ridicule and in a strong feeling of pan-Mapuche, ethnic solidarity, vis-à-vis Chilean society. Even in the sphere of economic activity, some of the traditional ceremonial aspects of economic life persist. Mapuche ritual appears both as an expression of this social and ethnic solidarity and as its single most stabilizing and integrating force" (Faron, 1964:205).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, the Mapuche were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, the Mapuche were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the society is coterminous with the religious group, there is no system for assigning religious affiliation other than being born into a specific lineage.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of recruitment efforts.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: When examining the Mapuche in the context of their own society (i.e. not taking the larger Chilean government into account), it is evident that the religious sphere is not distinguished from the political sphere. Religious beliefs are integrated throughout Mapuche society, and the society is coterminous with the religious group. (see Faron, 1964:205).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6:Large or Impressive Structures, [Note, Identical to SCCS variable 66] "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The Mapuche do not have a singular head of the polity or head of the religion.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to having political and social influence, chiefs have a significant ritual leadership role (see Faron, 1964:16-17).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: This entry focuses on the vicinity of Temuco. There are no population figures available for this specific region. "There are an estimated 200,000 Araucanian Indians living on more than 2,000 small reservations scattered over a large area in central Chile known as the Frontera or Araucanía. Well over half of these Indians are settled in Cautín and Malleco provinces, the heart of the indigenous zone" (Faron, 1961:5).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "It is because of her ability: to cure illness and prevent death that people place their faith and trust in a machi. She always inspires a good deal of awe on the part of her clients and people in general, for she spiritually enters the realm of supernatural beings and forces. In a manner of speaking, the machi enters the holy of holies, communes with and is possessed by the forces of good and is thereby able to control the forces of evil. The machi is the most continually active member of any community in dealing with right and wrong. Her livelihood and her spiritual survival depend on preoccupation with Mapuche morality. Her close association with the sacred realm of Mapuche society symbolizes her separateness from ordinary people" (Faron, 1964:138).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Faron, 1964:138

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "All machi, and therefore, all neophytes, must demonstrate exceptional sensitivity to dream experiences, perspicacity in interpersonal relationships, good memories, and adeptness in making herbal remedies for most common illnesses. Much of their reputation in curing the more common fevers and malaise depends on their store of remedies; only machi with extraordinary ability to enter trance are sought out for the curing of illnesses which appear to forebode death" (Faron, 1964:140).

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: "Shamanistic lore is sometimes learned from one's mother or a woman on the mother's side of the family, but a machi does not, according to the few genealogies I

was able to obtain, inherit power from one's mother or from a close kinswoman" (Faron, 1964:140).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "Whatever the nature of inheritance, whether or not a woman trains to become a machi depends on her personal capabilities and special qualities, as well as on the availability of a teacher who appreciates them, and the willingness or ability of her parents to pay the cost of instruction" (Faron, 1964:140).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures among the Mapuche.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6:Large or Impressive Structures, [Note, Identical to SCCS variable 66] "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6:Large or Impressive Structures, [Note, Identical to SCCS variable 66] "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of iconography.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Nomelafken, or wenumapu (used mostly in the eastern sector of Mapucheland), is the final resting place of the dead. Upon death, the term for soul (am) is dropped and either pelu or alwe is used. Pelu is generally used in association with the spirit during the period between physical demise and burial in the cemetery, during the wake, the removal of the corpse to its place of exhibition (temporary burial), and the four days after final (secondary) interment. After final burial, if the people are satisfied that the spirit has begun its journey to the resting place of the dead, the term for soul might change to alwe (wandering spirit). When a great measure of finality is noted, further terminological change takes place, and the departed spirit is subsumed within the collective pu am, pu laku, or the even more generalized kuifiche. There it should remain" (Faron, 1964:56).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "It is commonly believed that the soul (am) is able to leave the body during sleep or illness" (Faron, 1964:74).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Nomelafken, or wenumapu (used mostly in the eastern sector of Mapucheland), is the final resting place of the dead" (Faron, 1964:56).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Outside Mapucheland, the exact location sometimes conceived as an island (nomelafken) far to the west and sometimes as a place in the sky (wenumapu), are found the vast majority of benevolent ancestral spirits" (Faron, 1964:65).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Outside Mapucheland, the exact location sometimes conceived as an island (nomelafken) far to the west and sometimes as a place in the sky (wenumapu), are found the vast majority of benevolent ancestral spirits" (Faron, 1964:65).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "Outside Mapucheland, the exact location sometimes conceived as an island (nomelafken) far to the west and sometimes as a place in the sky (wenumapu), are found the vast majority of benevolent ancestral spirits" (Faron, 1964:65).

– I don't know

Notes: "There are many divergent accounts of the fate of a soul after death and burial. Most often it is said that the spirits of the dead go to kütralmapu ('fireland'), a place associated with the sun; but some say that disembodied souls go to a place above the earth, wenumapu; or underground, minchemapu; or across the sea, n-omel-afken, or karkul-afken. I could arrive at no clear idea of the distinctions among these various other worlds, nor could I discover what class of souls go to each place, except in the case of witches whose spirits go to the cave or renü with which they were formerly associated" (Titiev, 1951:107).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: "...it was explicitly stated that the souls of the dead are not reborn on earth in the bodies of babies" (Titiev, 1951:108).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding treatments for adherents' corpses.

Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cremation.

Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mummification.

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Preparations for interment are made as soon as relatives and friends have had time to assemble. The body is enclosed either in a conventional coffin or in an old-fashioned "canoe" made by bisecting a stout tree trunk lengthwise. Each half is then hollowed out, the body is put into the lower half, and the upper segment is fitted over it and tied on as a lid" (Titiev, 1951:104).

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Because corpses are interred within coffins, it can be assumed that the corpses are extended.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: Because corpses are interred within coffins, it can be assumed that the corpses are extended.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "...the practice of smoking the body of an important person still exists, although it is uncommon" (Faron, 1964:82).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: "After the deposit of food, drink, and other gifts, the grave is filled in and covered with a heavy log. It was explained that this is done to protect the body from inclement weather, to keep out wild animals, and to prevent witches from snatching the remains for conversion into a *witranalwe*" (Titiev, 1951:106).

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "The important aspect for this study, in any case, is that the corpse is not quickly disposed of, not immediately interred in its final resting place, but is handled in a deliberate, temporary manner which may be singled out for analytic purposes as the first phase of the funeral ceremony. In effect, final burial is secondary burial" (Faron, 1964:84).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: "At one time it seems to have been the custom to kill a man's favorite horse over his grave and to bury it in an adjacent plot, but this is no longer done" (Titiev, 1951:106).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Preparations for interment are made as soon as relatives and friends have had time to assemble. The body is enclosed either in a conventional coffin or in an old-fashioned "canoe" made by bisecting a stout tree trunk lengthwise. Each half is then hollowed out, the body is put into the lower half, and the upper segment is fitted over it and tied on as a lid. Food, wine, tools, and offerings contributed by friends and acquaintances are placed inside" (Titiev, 1951:104).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For a full description of burial customs, see Faron, 1964 pp.81-91, as well as questions below.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "The Araucanians prefer spacious cemeteries, completely enclosed and entered through a single gate which can be locked. Orientation is generally to the west, and members of both sexes may be buried side by side, but one section is usually set apart for children" (Titiev, 1951:105).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Mapuche have a numerous pantheon, consisting of major, minor, and lesser deities. Respectively, these may be called ethnic, regional, and lineage deities" (Faron, 1964:50).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note: identical to Ethnographic Atlas column 34] indicates that a high god is "present and active in human affairs but not supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). "...ñenechen is a Supreme Being for most Mapuche" (Faron, 1964:50).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The location of the abode of the Supreme Being is not known; it is spoken of as wenumapu—a word used also when speaking of sky, celestial regions, heaven" (Hilger, 1957:141).

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No
Notes: The Mapuche do not have a monarch.
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No
Notes: The Mapuche do not have a monarch.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No
Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that ñenechen has a kin relation to elites. Kin relations between the living and the supernatural occur between ancestral spirits.
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No
Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that ñenechen has a kin relation to elites. Kin relations between the living and the supernatural occur between ancestral spirits.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: "General misfortune involving flood, crop failure, large-scale death of animals, and the like is not attributed to any specific force of evil, but rather to a pervading malevolence and a feeling that ñenechen has been insufficiently or imperfectly propitiated. There is a partial acceptance of hardship and an attempt to supplicate ñenechen in public ceremonial, in order to control the machinations of the collective wekufe, generalized evil" (Faron, 1964:65).
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– I don't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes
Notes: "While it is to ñenechen that final appeal is made, for only he is able to control

the minor gods, the closest ties between man and the supernatural beings (which are clearly discernible as deities of significance) exist between the Mapuche and the regional gods and goddesses" (Faron, 1964:52).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of the high god (ñenechen) communicating with the living.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The most dramatic aspects of social action involved in the central concept of Mapuche religious morality revolves around the belief that ancestors are sacred and influential spirits whose existence regulates and depends upon human moral conduct" (Faron, 1964:4).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Among the several visible forms assumed by ancestors are 'hawks of the sun' (antüpaiñamko), a designation used by the Mapuche and employed here to symbolize all ancestral spirits" (Faron, 1964:4). "The dead visit the living. They are seen in dreams, in lifelike form, or as birds or other creatures of good or bad omen. They are also seen in waking moments, but only as distorted images of their former selves, or in nonhuman guise" (Faron, 1964:6).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Among the several visible forms assumed by ancestors are 'hawks of the sun' (antüpaiñamko), a designation used by the Mapuche and employed here to symbolize all ancestral spirits. Hawks of the sun, then, are beneficent ancestor spirits who intervene in the affairs of the living, who are responsible to the living, and, at the same time, who govern human conduct" (Faron, 1964:4).

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: "Returned spirits make their presence known in a number of ways besides their appearances in dreams. They remain near the house for the purpose of observing the living, to watch over their former possessions, or to take one of their family with them to the afterworld" (Faron, 1964:58).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "These [ancestral] spirits—hawks of the sun—on occasion descend to earth and return to Mapucheland, either to remind their kinsmen of certain neglected obligations or to assist them in various ways. Benevolent ancestral spirits may be characterized as pneumatic, and may be otiose, but they are capable of becoming active in that sphere of the supernatural which connects man and god" (Faron, 1964:65).

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Linked to moral code

Notes: "Hawks of the sun [ancestral spirits] are tethered to specific unilineal kingroups. When the bonds which hold them are loosed or broken because of some infraction of the moral code—caused by the negligence of their heirs—they are in danger of being ensnared by wily sorcerers and forced to perform evil deeds in the night. Once in the clutches of a sorcerer the spirit is completely and eternally helpless. There is no way back for the spirit, no way in which its living relatives are able to free it from serving evil or from doing harm to them" (Faron, 1964:63).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Returned spirits make their presence known in a number of ways besides their appearances in dreams. They remain near the house for the purpose of observing the living, to watch over their former possessions, or to take one of their family with them to the afterworld" (Faron, 1964:58).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "There is a universal belief among the Mapuche that spirits return to earth and make their presence known in dreams. These are called 'dream spirits' (peuma), indicating another change in the essence of departed spirits" (Faron, 1964:58).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Wekufe is the generic term for all malevolent spirits and forces in the world. As a descriptive device, since the Mapuche do not order as much as they lump these forces of evil, they may be categorized as animistic and placed into three groups: animals, natural phenomena, and ghosts. Any evil spirit has the power, or is able through the manipulation of a kalku, to assume the form of a being representative of any of the three groups, and to make

itself visible and invisible at will" (Faron, 1964:66).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The minor gods, while under the control of ñenechen, retain a certain freedom of action. Some of them are described as picturesque, although in no sense malevolent. For example, kupukafucha and his wife, kupukakushe—god and goddess of abundance—do not automatically bestow man with rich crops and herds. They do answer prayers if properly addressed, and they are beseeched to intercede before ñenechen on behalf of mankind" (Faron, 1964:52).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "But once any particular [human] spirit has fallen [into the clutches of evil magical practitioners] and has become converted to a ghost, it remains evil and continues to inflict harm on anyone, usually at the behest of a kalku, sometimes at its own discretion, always to obtain its victim's blood. The contaminated spirit is no longer identifiable as a specific ancestor. It is invisible, but it may be seen on occasion by humans in one of several stereotyped forms that it may assume. Once contaminated, it becomes a force of generalized evil" (Faron, 1964:63).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Mythical ancestors are included among those generalized deities supplicated on a regional, but apparently not on a pan-Mapuche, basis. For example, two ancestral figures who drowned in the Toltén River near where it empties into the Pacific Ocean are today visible in the form of birds (hawks of the sun) which occasionally appear at the ñillatun ceremonies held by the residents of the region" (Faron, 1964:60).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The Mapuche have a numerous pantheon, consisting of major, minor, and lesser deities" (Faron, 1964:50).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: "The Mapuche have a numerous pantheon, consisting of major, minor, and lesser deities. Respectively, these may be called ethnic, regional, and lineage deities" (Faron, 1964:50). "The principal notion which emerges, despite what may be said about the special importance of these gods for certain regions, is that in the concept of multiple deities is seen a progression from man to deity, expressed on the one hand as a hierarchical ordering of major, minor, and lesser deities, and on the other in the knowledge that all Mapuche may in time become hawks of the sun" (Faron, 1964:52).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note: identical to Ethnographic Atlas column 34] indicates that a high god is "present and active in human affairs but not supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, regional ancestors do not have particular concern for the living (Faron, 1964:60). Local/recent ancestors are generally guardian figures, and no ethnographic evidence is present to indicate they are actively involved with human morality.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "According to Cooper's sources the Supreme Being did not concern Himself with the moral order of things; nor did the state of souls in the future life depend on reward or punishment meted out by Him (1946, p. 742). My informants were agreed that punishment was meted out to individuals and/or all the people while they were on earth" (Hilger, 1957:140).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "According to Cooper's sources the Supreme Being did not concern Himself with the moral order of things; nor did the state of souls in the future life depend on reward or punishment meted out by Him (1946, p. 742). My informants were agreed that punishment was meted out to individuals and/or all the people while they were on earth" (Hilger, 1957:140).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "According to Cooper's sources the Supreme Being did not concern Himself with the moral order of things; nor did the state of souls in the future life depend on reward or punishment meted out by Him (1946, p. 742). My informants were agreed that punishment was meted out to individuals and/or all the people while they were on earth" (Hilger, 1957:140).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: " 'N(ə)nechén sends punishment by sending weather like we are having this summer [drought],' said one[informant]; 'He punishes us because so many Mapuche do not like to pray, and are not praying.'" (Hilger, 1957:140).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "What constitutes Mapuche morality? All institutionalized behavior is in concordance with the moral order which permeates society, aberrant behavior being defined in relation to departure from this code. Patterned kinship relationships are moral relationships, in this sense, and social interaction between nonkin is as well conditioned by the general order of moral values. A single moral system, therefore, defines proper and improper relationships throughout Mapucheland, among Mapuche themselves, and between Mapuche and outsiders (winka). This moral code is in turn anchored to the relationship which exists between the living and the dead, the rights and duties which exist between them in the context of Mapuche religious lore. Morality has supernatural sanction. It is the supernatural sanctions of the moral system expressed in life relationships with which this study is most concerned—specifically those human relationships which may be described as ritual or ceremonial" (Faron, 1964:10).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The only universal food tabus apply to snakes and frogs. In addition, young people are forbidden to eat sheep testicles, lest girls develop pains in the breasts and boys suffer from aching testes. Growing children are not allowed to eat bone marrow, because it is regarded as a "watery" substance that will retard their development. Furthermore, to ensure that they will not engage in premature sexual activity, adolescent girls may not eat unripe fruit, and grown women must abstain from fish lest, like them, they refuse to settle into permanent homes" (Titiev, 1951:30).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for required participation in small-scale rituals.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: The most important ceremony of the Mapuche is ñillatun, which is concerned with agricultural prosperity and the community's general well-being and protection from harm. The generalized ancestors, local regional gods, and creator god are all propitiated during this time. Participation does not appear to be explicitly mandatory, but almost everyone gathers for this event and, "The delegation of responsibilities throughout the participant groups results in a truly collective representation of the moral community on all occasions of ñillatun. People both desire and feel obligated, before their ancestors and the community, to accept ritual responsibility" (Faron, 1961:215). For a detailed description, see Faron, 1964 pp.93-101.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The ñillatun ceremonies are supervised by priests, chiefs, and elders (see Faron, 1964:93-101).

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Shortly before the date set for ñillatun, a select group of elders (the designated officials) goes to the ñillatun field to make it ready for the performance. This group is a separate, secret conclave from which all women and children are excluded" (Faron, 1964:96) "At the highest level of responsible participation stand the ñillatufe from the core reservations. They are instrumental in effecting a successful performance through the ritual assistance they lend the ñillatufe of the host reservation. Also, there are "captains" and "sergeants" who are responsible for relaying the orders of the ñillatufe to the throng, calling them forth to dance, to ride, and regulating the tempo of the dances, kindling the sacrificial fires and placing meat on the altar, and maintaining general order and respect throughout the long ceremony" (Faron, 1961:215).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Mapuche have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, according to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent), the Mapuche have patrilineal descent with small, localized communities. Further, the Mapuche live in segmented communities where a marked tendency toward local exogamy is also specifically reported. Patrilineal lineages are present, and of modest size. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22.

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "There are 10 state rural schools in the Araucanian country today, intended for Araucanian children; only one area is without a school. When teachers are available, Araucanian children attend well. Most persons older than 20 had attended school only a very short time, if at all" (Hilger, 1957:303).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Mapuche interact with the Chilean government. "In its body of Indian legislation, the Chilean government deals with Mapuche reservations as a totality. However, in actual practice at the local level of administration, the segmentary nature of Mapuche political units compels government agencies to deal with single reservations and individual chiefs in matters pertaining to reservation land. In this sense, each reservation is an autonomous political unit with respect to other reservations" (Faron, 1961:102).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes are paid to the Chilean Government. "A tax is levied against land owned by Araucanians, something the Araucanians find incomprehensible and talk about with animated resentment" (Hilger, 1957:174).

Enforcement

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Reservation status entitles the Mapuche to special consideration in Indian courts and in the Ministry of Lands and Colonization. As Chilean citizens, though, the Mapuche also have a series of rights and obligations irrespective of reservation status which brings them under the jurisdiction of national courts, the authority of which is backed by the Chilean police force, military organization, and penal institutions" (Faron, 1961:102).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Reservation status entitles the Mapuche to special consideration in Indian courts and in the Ministry of Lands and Colonization. As Chilean citizens, though, the Mapuche also have a series of rights and obligations irrespective of reservation status which brings them under the jurisdiction of national courts, the authority of which is backed by the Chilean police force, military organization, and penal institutions" (Faron, 1961:102).

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Reservation status entitles the Mapuche to special consideration in Indian courts and in the Ministry of Lands and Colonization. As Chilean citizens, though, the Mapuche also have a series of rights and obligations irrespective of reservation status which brings them under the jurisdiction of national courts, the authority of which is backed by the Chilean police force, military organization, and penal institutions" (Faron, 1961:102).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Chiefs enforce customary law (admapu), but Chilean law is most enforced. "On the one hand there is the supreme political authority of the Chilean government. This is mediated at the local level through Indian-affairs officers, courts, and police. On the other hand there is Mapuche customary law enforced by chiefs. The chiefs mediate Chilean law on the reservations. To the extent, however, that the chief's role has been usurped by governmental action, by an effort to break up the reservations and deal individually with the Mapuche as Chilean nationals, chieftainship has been considerably curtailed" (Faron, 1961:114).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Reservation status entitles the Mapuche to special consideration in Indian courts and in the Ministry of Lands and Colonization. As Chilean citizens, though, the Mapuche also have a series of rights and obligations irrespective of reservation status which brings them under the jurisdiction of national courts, the authority of which is backed by the Chilean police force, military organization, and penal institutions" (Faron, 1961:102).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– I don't know

Notes: Araucanian is the Mapuche ritual language (Faron, 1964:50). It is unclear if Araucanian is written or exclusively spoken.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Mapuche rely primarily on intensive agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry, gathering, and fishing provide additional food sources. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Mapuche rely primarily on intensive agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry, gathering, and fishing provide additional food sources. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.